

Intermediate Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan

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1. Executive Summary

D7.5 “Intermediate Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan” is an update of D7.4 “Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan” (submitted in M6, December 2022) [1]. The focus of this deliverable remains on effective dissemination, communication, and maximisation of the impact of our key results.

The document includes a brief introduction of greenSPEED and the deliverable’s objectives, followed by an update of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (chapter 3) and the Exploitation (Chapter 4). A conclusion is provided in chapter 5.

D7.6 “Final Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan” will provide a final update of this deliverable in M42. Until then, the outlined activities and plans of D7.5 will be further refined and executed, keeping the dynamic nature of the industries and stakeholders in mind.

Keywords: Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, Clustering Activities

2. Introduction

D7.5 follows and updates D7.4 “Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan” submitted in M6 (December 2022) [1]. The aim is to raise awareness, maximise the impact of communication and promotion activities and reach a wider audience. In addition, the plan shall support the exploitation of the greenSPEED Key Results (KR).

This chapter briefly introduces greenSPEED and explains the objectives. Chapter 3 focuses on the updated Dissemination and Communication Plan, while Chapter 4 describes the exploitation. Chapter 5 concludes the document with a short summary.

2.1 greenSPEED in a Nutshell

The market for electromobility is growing steadily, series production of battery electric vehicles (BEVs) is in full swing, and OEMs are introducing BEVs in their product portfolio. Unfortunately, the lithium-ion cell technology that powers these vehicles is still not supplied by the European industry. Moreover, while lithium-ion technology is the path to greener and more sustainable mobility and other mobile applications, the cell manufacturing process is still very energy-consuming and uses environmentally harmful substances.

greenSPEED addresses two main drawbacks of current battery cell production techniques a) the high energy consumption of the individual production steps; and b) the introduction of new production processes that do not require organic casting solvents. Both, in combination with the increase in energy density, will lead to a significant reduction in the cost of lithium-ion cells. The greenSPEED project provides solutions for new sustainable electrode and cell manufacturing processes with reduced energy consumption, lower carbon footprint and zero emissions of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs). greenSPEED aims to secure Europe’s leadership in the production of batteries with a lower carbon footprint by improving production processes and establishing them in Europe.

2.2 Objectives

D7.5 outlines of the project’s dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy and action plan. The aim is to support the objectives of greenSPEED and to provide a platform for further dissemination and communication of the results and to support their exploitation.

3. Dissemination and Communication Plan

In a first step, a Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan has been developed in the course of D7.4. In the following chapters, updates will be provided to reflect the changes and activities over the last 12 months since the submission of D7.4.

3.1 Target Groups

The greenSPEED consortium has already identified target groups at the proposal stage and in the first six months of the project, specifically in D7.4. For this list no update is required:

- External Stakeholders (including all OEMs, TIER1 & TIER2 supplier, standardisation bodies as well as policy and decision makers)
- Scientific Community (including research centres and tertiary education institutions)
- Related R&D Projects and Networks
- General Public

3.2 Key Messages

The following key messages have been defined in D7.4:

- greenSPEED will develop new solutions for a more sustainable electrode and cell manufacturing processes that reduce energy consumption and lower the carbon footprint.
- greenSPEED will develop green and sustainable processes for electrode production.
- greenSPEED will create green, sustainable, stable, and cost-efficient material sets as well as production processes and techniques for lithium-ion cells.
- greenSPEED strengthens the competitiveness of the European battery industry by achieving European leadership in battery production with a lower carbon footprint.
- greenSPEED will implement the capabilities of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and digital twins in the cell production process to improve the understanding of and the control over different production steps.
- greenSPEED will combine the unique technologies of the European battery industry, organise R&D collaboration and prototype development, to demonstrate a high-performance low-footprint automotive battery.
- greenSPEED will overcome the need of a primer layer applied on the Aluminium current collector for the dry-processed cathode, which is an additional cost bearer and has a lower energy density.
- greenSPEED combines European industry and research for safe production of cost-efficient, European lithium-ion batteries.

As these key messages still apply for the project, they have not been updated. However, the following key messages have been added for the updated Dissemination and Communication Plan:

- greenSPEED innovates battery production for a greener tomorrow.
- By reducing energy consumption, lowering the carbon footprint achieving ZERO emissions of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs), and immediately reducing costs, greenSPEED is leading the way towards a more sustainable future for battery cells.

3.3 D&C Planning

To keep an overview of the upcoming posts, they are planned as seen in Figure 3-1. In this list, the social media and blog posts are being tracked. This gives an overview of the planned topics, authors, and the current status, including the planned publication date. The list is updated on a regular basis.

MONTH	PUBLICATION DATE	PLATFORM	TOPIC	VISUAL	AUTHOR	RESPONSIBLE VIF	Link	STATUS
M17 November 2023								
CW46	13. November 2023	LinkedIn	EARPA Blog Post	link to greenSPEED blog	VIF	Medina	Link to Post	Published
CW46	13. November 2023	LinkedIn	Video - geladen Podcast	link to YouTube video	VIF	Alex	Link to Post	Published
CW47	22. November 2023	LinkedIn	Flyer/2-pager	GIF & link to greenSPEED website	VIF	Medina	Link to Post	Published
CW48	29. November 2023	LinkedIn	IBPC 2023	picture	ZSW	Medina	Link to Post	Published
M18 December 2023								
CW49			break					
CW50	14. December 2023	Blog Post/Website	Partner Interview VIF	picture	VIF	Alex	Link to Post	Published
CW50	14. December 2023	LinkedIn	Partner Interview VIF	link to greenSPEED blog	VIF	Alex	Link to Blogpost	Published
CW51	20. December 2023	Blog Post/Website	greenSPEED Newsletter #1	document	VIF	Medina	Link to Blogpost	Published
CW51	20. December 2023	LinkedIn	greenSPEED Newsletter #1	link to greenSPEED blog	VIF	Medina	Link to Post	Published
CW51	22. December 2023	LinkedIn	holiday wishes	picture	VIF	Medina		Ready for Publication
CW52			break					
M19 January 2024								
CW1			break					
CW2	09. January 2024	LinkedIn	plans for the new year	picture	VIF	Medina		Under Review
CW3	17. January 2024	LinkedIn	Battery Heroes - intro new members	picture	VIF	Medina		Under Review
CW4	24. January 2024	Blog Post/Website	Partner Interview CFL	picture	CFL	Medina		Under Review
CW4	24. January 2024	LinkedIn	Partner Interview CFL	link to greenSPEED blog	VIF	Medina		Under Review
CW5	30. January 2024	LinkedIn	Q&A part 2	video	VIF	Medina		In Preparation

Figure 3-1: greenSPEED Dissemination and Communication Planner for Activity Tracking (Social Media & Website)

The D&C Planner is a guide to help plan the blog and LinkedIn posts. It is therefore flexible and new topics can be added at any time (e.g. when a new publication is accepted). This is also the reason why topics such as publications are not included in the planning, simply because it is not possible to plan the acceptance of papers. However, as soon as the information is received, the topics will be added to the planner.

Another benefit of this planning is that the blog and LinkedIn posts can also be scheduled for a specific date and time via the website and LinkedIn, which is a good way to plan ahead and also keep to the planned publication dates according to the planner.

3.4 Dissemination Channels and Activities – Update

The next chapters will focus on the selected channels and activities used within greenSPEED. The links below will lead to the website and social media accounts.

Link to the Website: www.greenspeed-project.eu

LinkedIn Account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/greenspeed-eu-project/>

YouTube Account: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCiBJCO_syQ4-AfuEW9G0YPw

3.4.1 Project Website Updates

The website is regularly updated by the dissemination and communication leader:

- The greenSPEED Explainer Video has been added to the homepage and can additionally be found in the Results & Media section (more details are included in Chapter 3.4.2).

- News & Events are included in the form of bog post and additionally shared via LinkedIn postings.
- Partner Initiatives have been updated on the website: [Partner Initiatives](#)
- In the Results & Media section, documents are available for download: [Results & Media](#)
 - Information Material available for download: [Project Introduction](#) & [Flyer/2-pager](#)
 - Public Deliverables available for download: [D7.1 greenSPEED Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan](#); [D7.2 greenSPEED Initial Data Management Plan](#); [D7.3 greenSPEED Project Identity and Web Presence](#); [D7.4 greenSPEED Preliminary Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan](#)

The detailed explanation of the website can be found in D7.3 “Project Identity and Web Presence” [2].

3.4.2 Project Videos

During the first project year, the consortium has been working on an explainer video. The goal is to present greenSPEED in more detail and make the objectives and content of the project more accessible to the general public.

The video starts with “*getting electrical energy to the right place at the right time can be difficult*” to show that Lithium-ion batteries seem like the obvious solution in case one needs a source of power on the go (for example in electric cars) or when there is no sun or wind. This is followed by common challenges and information the public receives and hears, such as “*production is dangerous, toxic, very energy-consuming (...)*”.

Here the introduction to the greenSPEED project starts by explaining the methods used within the project to produce a cheaper and safer lithium-ion battery cell.

The video is available on the greenSPEED YouTube Channel: [greenSPEED EU Project: Innovating Battery Production for a Greener Tomorrow](#)

Figure 3-2: greenSPEED Explainer Video

Since its release on 17 February 2023, the video has been viewed 821 times (Status: 14. December 2023). The analysis of the video shows that most viewers were search for the following two terms to find the video, which are both included in the video caption (Figure 3-2):

- greenspeed
- volatile organic compounds

The video was shared via the greenSPEED YouTube account, the LinkedIn page and the greenSPEED website. Partners have also reposted the video on their LinkedIn pages. The video is also a great tool to link to in blog posts, for example, to provide further details. This has been done for the blog post by Virtual Vehicle: [greenSPEED: Innovating Battery Production - Virtual Vehicle](#)

Coordinated by Virtual Vehicle, greenSPEED brings together industry and research in Europe. The expertise and knowledge of participants from the automotive industry, technology companies, research and knowledge hubs from Germany, France, Austria, Luxembourg, and the Netherlands will be bundled, and the know-how will be further developed to achieve the goal of Europe's leadership in the production of batteries with a low carbon footprint. greenSPEED is also part of the "Battery Heroes", a cluster created by the four partner projects from the same call to further strengthen their cooperation. The goal is to exchange ideas and plan joint dissemination activities to create synergies.

More information about [Battery Heroes](#)

[greenSPEED Website](#)

Follow us on [LinkedIn](#)

greenSPEED EU Project: Innovating Battery Production for a Greener Tomorrow

Li-ion

Watch on [YouTube](#)

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Figure 3-3: greenSPEED project introduction - Virtual Vehicle Blog Post

3.4.3 Social Media – LinkedIn

The YouTube and LinkedIn accounts for greenSPEED were created at the beginning of the project. Since then, regular updates have been posted. LinkedIn is greenSPEED's main social media channel. YouTube is only used to upload the project videos (which are then shared via LinkedIn and the website). This chapter will therefore focus on LinkedIn.

3.4.3.1 Account and Content Creation

The LinkedIn account is managed by the Dissemination & Communication leader Virtual Vehicle, who is also the project coordinator. The general goal is to have at least two posts per month, ideally one post per week. However, this will depend on the content that is currently available. The content available is regularly discussed at the monthly WP Leaders meetings, where past and planned activities are reported. After the meeting, ViF will follow up with the respective WP Leader to discuss potential posts for the website or LinkedIn.

3.4.3.2 Followers

Currently, greenSPEED has 302 followers on LinkedIn (Status 21. December 2023). The LinkedIn follower demographics based on the industry show the following five areas as the TOP 5 among the followers:

1. Research Services
2. Motor Vehicle Manufacturing
3. Semiconductor Manufacturing
4. Higher Education
5. Appliances, Electrical, and Electronics Manufacturing

The detailed list is shown in Figure 3-4. The industries shown in the figure are based on the information in the individual profiles and are for guidance only.

Figure 3-4: greenSPEED LinkedIn Follower Demographics based on (LinkedIn) Industry

3.4.3.3 Including Partners, Related Initiatives and Hashtags

When a LinkedIn post is created, the associated partners and initiatives are also mentioned. This is to ensure a wider reach, and the site owners are notified of each new post, making it more likely that it will be reposted. In addition, the hashtags selected are also very important. The first thing to do when choosing them is to check how many followers they have. For example:

- #innovation (38,467,655 followers)
- #sustainability (13,179,012 followers)
- #lithiumionbatteries (5,135 followers)
- #horizoneurope (2,713 followers)

Based on the number of followers, the most appropriate hashtags are chosen. This ensures that the right audience is targeted, and that reach can be increased by using popular hashtags.

3.4.3.4 General Observations

In general, it can be said that postings with additional media (e.g. images, videos, links with images) generate more impressions and engagement than a posting without any additional visuals. This is something we keep in mind when preparing the posts. It is also important to link the related partners and initiatives to improve the visibility and outreach of the postings.

3.4.4 Events and Conferences

As part of the project, events and conferences attended by greenSPEED partners and upcoming events and conferences are tracked. The coordinator makes an updated list available directly in the greenSPEED SharePoint (see screenshot in Figure 3-5) to help the partners track and attend them. The partners can either update the list themselves or ask ViF to update it for them. By adding a short explanation of the activity, this helps to provide a quick overview and inspire other partners about what could be done.

Name of Event/Conference	Date	Location	Audience	Partner	Activity	Link	Participated
Ulm Electrochemical Talks (UECT)	06/14/2023	Ulm, Germany	Scientific community	ZSW	Poster presentation	https://uect.de/	yes
Ulm Electrochemical Talks (UECT)	06/14/2023	Ulm, Germany	Scientific community	BMW	Project presentation	https://uect.de/	yes
EARPA Form Forum	10/17/2023	Brussels, Belgium		VIF	Company booth with project introduction	https://www.earpa.eu/...	yes
International Battery Production Conferenc...	07. - 09. November 2023	Braunschweig, Germany	Scientific community	ZSW	Presentation		yes
TRA 2024	15. - 18. April 2024	Dublin, Ireland		VIF	Booth	https://traconference.e...	
Ulm Electrochemical Talks	4. - 5. June 2025	Ulm, Germany		ZSW	tbd	https://uect.de/	
EARPA Form Forum	30. September - 01. October 2024	Brussels, Belgium		VIF	tbd	https://www.earpa.eu/...	

Figure 3-5: Tracking of relevant Events and Conferences

3.4.5 Publications

Most of the submitted papers are still under review and results are expected in Q1/2024. An update will be provided in the next D&C&E plan.

3.4.6 Newsletter and Press Release

The periodic newsletter has been shared in month 18 via the website and social media. The goal of the newsletter was to provide an overview of the greenSPEED activities so far. It is also intended to provide a first overview of the project progress so far. It can be found [here](#).

A press release is currently in preparation to summarise the first 18 project months and inform the public. The consortium has decided to release it after month 18 instead of month 12 to provide more information on the project progress. The press release will also be available on the website once prepared and approved by the consortium.

3.4.7 Cohesion Activities – the Battery Heroes

Part of the greenSPEED Dissemination and Communication plan is the exchange with related partner projects and initiatives. In D7.4, the partner projects BatWoMan, NoVOC and GIGAGREEN have been introduced. All four projects are funded under the same Horizon Europe call. Between M6 and M18 of the greenSPEED project, the partner projects have been in regular contact and have decided on a cluster name: the **Battery Heroes**.

The Battery Heroes are engaged in joint cohesion activities to exchange knowledge and share information about the challenges they face. Moreover, the joint dissemination and communication activities aim to increase the outreach of the individual project activities and the cluster activities in general.

3.4.7.1 New Cluster Members

In December 2023, the Battery Heroes welcomed two new members: BATMACHINE and GIGABAT. Both projects are funded under the HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01-04 call.

3.4.7.2 Regular Meetings

Regular meetings are now scheduled between the Battery Heroes approximately every 4 weeks. From each project, at least one representative joins the meetings. These regular meetings help us to not only exchange ideas for joint activities but also exchange challenges we are facing in our projects and best-practices.

For the preparation of the upcoming Transport Research Arena (TRA), the Battery Heroes had a hybrid workshop to prepare ideas and a strategy on what we want to show during the event.

In the December meeting, also a representative from the LIPLANET initiative has been presented to discuss upcoming collaboration opportunities. It has been decided that they will also join the regular meetings from now on. In addition, the two new cluster members are also joining the regular meetings.

3.4.7.3 Joint Communication

A website has been created to provide a short overview of the Battery Heroes: <https://batteryheroes.eu/>

In addition, regular LinkedIn postings (Figure 3-6, Figure 3-7) and blog posts (Figure 3-8) are shared by the Battery Heroes.

THE 4 BATTERY HEROES

- batwo man**: Carbon Neutral European Battery Cell Production with Sustainable, Innovative Processes and 3D Electrode Design to Manufacture
www.batwoman.eu
- GIGAGREEN**: Towards the Sustainable Giga-Factory: Developing Green Cell Manufacturing Processes
www.gigagreenproject.eu
- NOVOC**: Eliminating VOC from Battery Manufacturing Through Dry or Wet Processing
www.novoc.eu
- GREEN SPEED**: Green and Sustainable Processes for Electrode Production
www.greenspeed-project.eu

www.batteryheroes.eu

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greenSPEED EU Project
294 followers
7mo •

Introducing today: **the Battery Heroes**

Together with our partner projects, we aim to use the synergies for joint clustering activities:

- BatWoMan**: Coordinated by **AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH**, BatWoMan develops new sustainable and cost-efficient Li-ion battery cell production concepts, paving the way towards carbon-neutral cell production within the EU.
- GIGAGREEN project**: Coordinated by **Politecnico di Torino**, GIGAGREEN proposes a structured research plan to develop and scale up novel electrode and cell component manufacturing processes that follow a Design to Manufacture approach.
- NOVOC**: Coordinated by **RISE Research Institutes of Sweden**, NOVOC aims to design, demonstrate and compare aqueous and dry electrode manufacturing as

Figure 3-6: Introduction of the Battery Heroes - greenSPEED LinkedIn Posting

Figure 3-7: Battery Heroes – Communication via LinkedIn examples

Figure 3-8: Battery Heroes – Blog Post examples

3.4.7.4 Joint Activities and Events

Currently, the Battery Heroes plan their participation in the Transport Research Arena (TRA) Conference, taking place 15th – 18th April 2024 in Dublin, Ireland. On the one hand, there will be a joint booth of the Battery Heroes and on the other hand it is planned to apply for a special session. The second point is currently still unknown as we are waiting for further information from the organisers.

In addition to that, it is planned to also introduce the cluster shortly at various events where the projects are participating. For example, the Battery Heroes have been presented at the EARPA Form Forum (17th – 18th October 2023 in Brussels, Belgium) at the Virtual Vehicle booth. At the booth, Virtual Vehicle presented the company and numerous projects that are coordinated

by them. There, they also included the Battery Heroes in a short pitch and the flyer, which is also available on the greenSPEED website: [greenSPEED Flyer/2-pager](#)

The BATTERY HEROES

The BATTERY HEROES are engaged in joint cohesion activities to exchange knowledge and share information about the challenges they face. Moreover, the joint dissemination and communication activities aim to increase the outreach of individual project activities and the cluster activities in general.

The current members:

	Carbon Neutral European Battery Cell Production with Sustainable, Innovative Processes and 3D Electrode Design to Manufacture www.batwoman.eu
	Towards the Sustainable Giga-Factory: Developing Green Cell Manufacturing Processes www.gigagreenproject.eu
	Eliminating VOC from Battery Manufacturing Through Dry or Wet Processing www.novoc.eu
	Green and Sustainable Processes for Electrode Production www.greenspeed-project.eu

www.batteryheroes.eu

Get in touch with greenSPEED!

www.greenspeed-project.eu	
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TO WATCH THE PROJECT VIDEO

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Figure 3-9: greenSPEED Flyer (Page 2)

3.4.8 Participation in the Horizon Results Booster (HRB)

The Battery Heroes have decided to apply for the Horizon Results Booster as a cluster to further strengthen the joint dissemination and communication activities.

Within the cluster it was decided, together with the experts from the HRB, to go for Module B of the dissemination services. This module focuses on the creation of a common dissemination plan and supporting materials. So far, the cluster does not have a visual identity or a social media account. The cluster's dissemination and communication activities are done via the project's channels. The plan is to change this by creating a visual identity and a short video about the Battery Heroes. As of Mid-December 2023, the visual identity is being developed and based on that, a short video will be created. This is scheduled for Q1 in 2024.

4. Exploitation

Within this section, an overview of the Key Exploitable Results will be provided. The goal is to map selected Key Results against dissemination & communication activities.

4.1 Key Results and Mapping of Strategies

In Figure 4-1, six greenSPEED Key Results are presented. They have been identified during the proposal preparation and have been further refined during the project duration.

Figure 4-1: greenSPEED Key Results

All partners have filled in a survey on the defined Key Results (KR). In the following subchapter, three of these KR are further refined and potential dissemination & communication activities have been included. Due to the public nature of this deliverable, not all details will be shared to ensure that IP and future exploitation of the results is protected. This has been also defined in the greenSPEED Consortium Agreement (CA) [4].

The listed activities in the following could help to realise the full potential of the individual Key Results. However, specific activities have been adapted to the results. In the second reporting period, the potential activities will be reassessed and implemented as deemed appropriate.

4.1.1 Key Result 1 (KR1)

Table 4-1: Overview Key Result 1

Key Result 1: Anode with optimised material formulation and pre-lithiation process for ultra-high-capacity Li-ion cells	
Target Stakeholders	Cell manufacturer, OEMs, Tier 1 supplier (material & current collector), researchers & academia, equipment manufacturer, service providers, start-ups and SMEs, large enterprises, policy makers, funding agencies including EU & national agencies
Benefits for the Stakeholders	The pure silicon anode increases energy density, and the highly innovative production process reduces production time and costs; supporting processes to exploit this new technology are also established (pre-lithiation). Stakeholders such as OEMs benefit from increased driving range. Lithium-ion-based cells and battery systems feature the ambitions towards a CO ₂ neutral cell production (greener batteries). This KR also supports the elimination of expensive materials for anode production. In addition, stakeholders benefit from an increased and strengthened market share due to better competitiveness on the (global) market based on innovative and sustainable material and process developments. Moreover, this KR strengthens the know-how and a higher ranking in journals helps to increase the visibility. Publications further promote knowledge transfer.

Expected Technology Readiness Level [5] / Chapter 7	TRL 4-5
Country or location of intended exploitation	EU and Global

Potential Dissemination & Communication Activities for Key Result 1

- Prepare publications and/or white papers covering the innovative aspects of KR1 above state of the art, showcasing the processes used within greenSPEED and the potential impact on Europe (e.g. reduction of dependency on fossil fuels, support of the EU's policies).
- This will be accompanied by a press release highlighting the benefits of KR1 to reach the general public. By being open and transparent with the results of EU-funded projects, this will help to strengthen society's trust in science and the solutions developed (with the aim of leading to acceptance and adoption of the greenSPEED technology).
- Showcase the results in real-world scenarios to demonstrate the technology (e.g. videos, webinars).
- Participate in conferences, symposia, and networking events. This can be used as an opportunity to present the results to a wide audience and engage with experts to create future collaboration opportunities.
- Online presence through the greenSPEED website and social media. The partners will be encouraged to use their organisation's accounts to share updates as well.
- Incorporating the knowledge generated during the work on this result could be fed into curricula and lectures of the scientific greenSPEED partners. This could be an opportunity to strengthen human capital in Europe.
- Collaboration in further research projects with other organisations could help to further enhance credibility, develop and disseminate the results.

4.1.2 Key Result 2 (KR2)

Table 4-2: Overview Key Result 2

Key Result 2: Data driven Digital Twins for virtual support of production process steps of battery cells	
Target Stakeholders	Cell manufacturer, OEMs, battery producer, Tier 1 supplier (material & current collector), equipment manufacturer, researchers & academia, service providers, start-ups and SMEs, large enterprises, policy makers, funding agencies including EU & national agencies
Benefits for the Stakeholders	One goal in the sustainable production of lithium-ion cells is to increase production yield. A dry production process is more complex and is therefore supported by a data-driven digital twin. The aim is to make the process more robust and reduce waste during production. This is a necessity for the (eventual) industrialisation of cell production. This KR reduces the

	development and production time to market while reducing costs. It also supports the strengthening of know-how in the EU and open science practices through increased research and publication of results.
Expected Technology Readiness Level [5] / Chapter 7	TRL 5
Country or location of intended exploitation	EU and Global

Potential Dissemination & Communication Activities for Key Result 2

- Plan technical demonstrations and/or webinars (e.g. a live demonstration or a video demonstration) to showcase the result.
- Attend conferences and workshops to present the findings (either as publication, presentation, or keynote). This also provides an opportunity to engage with the stakeholders.
- Participation in networking events to engage with stakeholders. This helps to increase visibility and adoption of the technology.
- Website and social coverage through regular updates (e.g. videos, blog posts, case studies). Infographics, animations, or videos could be created to break-down the concept of KR2 and explain it in a simpler way.
- Press release on milestones, achievements etc. related to the key result. This will help to increase the audience and inform the public.
- Training programmes (e.g. in the form of online courses, on-site training, or training materials) could be an opportunity to educate potential users on the topic.
- Collaboration in further research projects with other organisations could help to further enhance credibility, develop and disseminate the results.
- Organising a hackathon could help to showcase the adaptability of the technology. By communicating it via different media channels to reach participants, it gives greenSPEED a bigger stage to explain this result.
- By working with standardisation bodies, the digital twins could be further developed to improve interoperability and facilitate wider adoption of the technology.

4.1.3 Key Result 3 (KR3)

Table 4-3: Overview Key Result 3

Key Result 3: Prototype cells with dry produced electrodes, established pre-lithiation process for optimised electrode utilisation and final industrial cell format	
Target Stakeholders	Cell manufacturer, OEMs, battery producer, Tier 1 supplier (material & current collector), equipment manufacturer, researchers & academia, service providers, start-ups and SMEs, large enterprises, policy makers, funding agencies including EU & national agencies, public/customers
Benefits for the Stakeholders	Increasing the energy density of lithium-ion cell technology by increasing the silicon content and eliminating toxic materials in

	<p>production reduces the complexity of the production steps and makes production facilities less expensive. This in turn reduces the overall cost of cell production and supports easier market entry, leading to easier and more affordable access to Electric Vehicles for customers. Through the green production process (dry coating), environmental protection and occupational safety is supported. In general, an increase of overall sustainability and improved LCA of the battery value chain is expected.</p> <p>The resulting (increased) know-how for large-scale cell production is well established in Europe and covers the entire value chain (leading to a growth of green, innovative, competitive, and sustainable battery manufacturing industry). This in return supports the goals to realise the European Green Deal.</p>
Expected Technology Readiness Level [5] / Chapter 7	TRL 5-6
Country or location of intended exploitation	EU and Global

Potential Dissemination & Communication Activities for Key Result 3

- Plan a joint (physical) event with the Battery Heroes, where each project can present its results. KR3 would be a great result to showcase at this event. This could also be done for technical demonstrations and/or webinars to showcase the results within the cluster.
- A press release could be an important activity to communicate this result and its impact.
- Participate in conferences/events/workshops to present the results (e.g. as publication, presentation).
- Online presence via website and social media to share regular updates (e.g. videos, blog posts, case studies), not only via the greenSPEED channels but also via the partner's channels and the partner initiatives.
- Also for KR3, the acquired knowledge can be incorporated into training programmes, curricula or lectures to further train and educate people.
- Further research projects could help to further develop the greenSPEED results. This should be done to ensure the sustainability of the results and the acquired knowledge.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this deliverable is to provide an update of D7.4 “Preliminary Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan”. Based on the described actions and plans in D7.4, the activities for M7-M18 have been further refined and (partly) executed. A detailed report of the performed activities will be provided in the course of the first reporting in Q1 2024.

Due to constant changes and developments, the outlined plan within this deliverable is regularly updated and adapted to meet the needs and expectations of the stakeholders. The greenSPEED consortium is aware of the open science practices as outlined in the Grant Agreement [3] and is committed to disseminate and communicate the results as open as possible. The detailed plan in D7.5 shall support these practices. In D7.6, the final Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan, a final update of this deliverable will be provided.

6. Abbreviations

Term	Definition
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicles
CA	Consortium Agreement
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EARPA	European Automotive Research Partners Association
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
KR	Key Result
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PU	Public
Q1	Quartal 1
R	Document, Report
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TRA	Transport Research Arena
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VOCs	Volatile Organic Compounds
WP	Work Package

7. References

- [1] greenSPEED Deliverable D7.4 “Preliminary Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan” v1.0, 2022-12-31
- [2] greenSPEED Deliverable D7.3 “Project Identity and Web Presence” v2.0, 2022-10-28
- [3] Grant Agreement Number 101069528 – greenSPEED, 2022-06-15
- [4] Consortium Agreement greenSPEED, Version [final 7.0], 2022-08-01
- [5] Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2024, 13. General Annexes (European Commission Decision C(2022)7550 of 6 December 2022)

A. Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

The TRLs referred to in this deliverable are based on the definitions of the Horizon Europe Work programme 2023-2024 – General Annexes (B) [5].

Table 7-1: Technology Readiness Level (TRL) Definition

TRL	Definition
TRL 1	Basic principles observed
TRL 2	Technology concept formulated
TRL 3	Experimental proof of concept
TRL 4	Technology validated in a lab
TRL 5	Technology validated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 6	Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 7	System prototype demonstration in an operational environment
TRL 8	System complete and qualified
TRL 9	Actual system proven in an operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies, or in space)